

POSTMORTEM CHANGES IN DOMESTIC ANIMALS: FORENSIC IMPLICATIONS AND HUMAN CASE COMPARISONS

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ABSTRACT

Thanatology, the study of death, examines physiological and biochemical postmortem changes, aiding forensic and veterolegal investigations. Death progresses through somatic and molecular stages, followed by immediate, early, and late postmortem changes. Immediate changes involve the cessation of vital functions, while early changes include pallor mortis, algor mortis, livor mortis, and rigor mortis. Late-stage changes involve decomposition, including autolysis and putrefaction, which lead to tissue breakdown. These changes help estimate the postmortem interval (PMI) and determine the cause of death. Algor mortis follows a sigmoid cooling pattern, with temperature dropping by 0.5°C per hour in summer and 0.7°C in winter, influenced by environmental and body factors. Postmortem caloricity, an exception, occurs in conditions like heatstroke. Livor mortis, the gravitational pooling of blood, fixes within 8–12 hours and provides clues to body positioning and toxicological causes. Rigor mortis follows Nysten's Rule, peaking at 12 hours and resolving by 36 hours, while cadaveric spasm occurs instantly, preserving the final position of muscles. Decomposition advances through autolysis and putrefaction, with green discoloration appearing within 12–18 hours. Gas formation leads to bloating and marbling, accelerating tissue breakdown. Casper's Dictum states that bodies decompose fastest in air, slower in water, and slowest underground. Adipocere, formed in moist conditions, preserves tissue for months, while mummification occurs in dry climates. Embalming extends preservation artificially. These postmortem changes collectively provide crucial forensic insights into death circumstances and Postmortem Interval (PMI) or Time Since Death (TSD) estimation.

Keywords : Embalming, Pallor Mortis, Suspended Animation, Supravital Period, and Thanatology.

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